

A proposed new algorithm for Source Updating

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ABSTRACT. A new algorithm for Source Updating in the GIS part of GDAAS is proposed. The main advantages compared with the old algorithm are greater computational efficiency (especially for outlier rejection) and robustness.

1 Introduction

A central algorithm in the Global Iterative Solution (GIS) for the Gaia data analysis is the Source Updating, in which the five (or six) astrometric parameters of (apparently single) stars are improved by a differential least-squares solution. The GIS consists of the cyclical running of Source Updating, Attitude Updating, Calibration Updating and Global Updating.

In principle the Source Updating is simply a least-squares solution of the n astrometric parameters of a given source (i.e., an apparently single star, or a quasar), where normally $n = 5$ or $n = 6$. The solution is made relative to a given set of astrometric parameters, which initially could be from the source matching (with a low precision of several mas), but later from a previous GIS iteration; hence the name updating.

The updating is based on m astrometric measurements, normally the AF1-11 centroid timings from all field-of-view transits of the source, but possibly including also across-scan positions from ASM and/or AF1. Typically there are of order $m \sim 1000$ observations.

The basic ‘observation equations’ to solve are

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \sim \mathbf{b} \pm \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} is an observation-equations matrix of dimension $m \times n$ (sometimes called the design matrix), \mathbf{b} an m -vector of residuals (in the sense observed *minus* computed), $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ an m -vector of measurement uncertainties (as derived from the centroiding algorithm), and \mathbf{x} an n -vector of corrections (or updates) to the astrometric parameters. The symbol \sim signifies that equality between the two sides of the observation equations is generally not possible, because the system is over-determined ($m \gg n$), but that general agreement within the measurement errors is sought. The i th element of \mathbf{b} is

$$b_i = y_i - f_i(\mathbf{a}) \quad (2)$$

where y_i is the measured (‘observed’) value and $f_i(\mathbf{a})$ the value computed from the model, using the current astrometric parameters \mathbf{a} . The elements of the observation equations matrix \mathbf{A} are

$$A_{ij} = \frac{\partial f_i(\mathbf{a})}{\partial a_j} \quad (3)$$

evaluated for the current parameter values. After solving for the corrections \mathbf{x} , the parameters are updated as

$$\mathbf{a} := \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{x} \tag{4}$$

(Special provision must be made for the updating of α , since the update is given as $\Delta\alpha \cos \delta$. See also Sect. 3.4.)

The updating algorithm should take the following considerations into account:

1. The m measurements are in general heteroscedastic (σ_i are not all the same), so a *weighted* least-squares solution should be used.
2. A small fraction of outliers must be expected, so the solution should be *robust* against errors of arbitrary size.
3. The model $f_i(\mathbf{a})$ is non-linear, so the updating process must be *iterated* until convergence. (Iteration is also needed to cope with outliers.)
4. Depending on the type of source and on the number and distribution of observations, it may be desirable to update less than the maximum set of $n = 6$ astrometric parameters. In fact $n = 5$ will be the normal case, but fewer may also be used. This corresponds to making solutions that are *constrained* to zero updates in some parameters.
5. On some sources the measurements may be *degenerate*, e.g., because there are too few observations, resulting in a non-unique least-squares solution. The algorithm should in such cases still produce a sensible update, if possible, and indicate that it is unreliable.
6. The calculation of $f_i(\mathbf{a})$ and its derivatives is time-consuming and recomputing them should be avoided when not strictly necessary.
7. Apart from the updated astrometric parameters, the algorithm should also supply their variances and correlations, together with suitable statistics and diagnostics.
8. The estimated variances should take into account error sources not included in the formal observation uncertainties σ .

The proposed new algorithm takes into account all these points, while the previous one only considered the first three.

2 The old algorithm

When making a least-squares solution one basically must choose between using or not using normal equations. Although using normal equations is computationally efficient and simple, it is often regarded as inferior mainly from the viewpoint of numerical stability. That is not a decisive argument against normals in the present case, however, because the equations are generally very well-conditioned and rounding errors are not a problem. The old Source Updating algorithm used normal equations, as described below.

In order to cope with the heteroscedasticity (item 1 above), we introduce the $m \times m$ weight matrix $\mathbf{W}_0 = \text{diag}(\sigma_1^{-2}, \dots, \sigma_m^{-2})$ and compute the normal equations as

$$\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{W}_0 \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{W}_0 \mathbf{b} \quad (5)$$

If the problem has full rank ($r = n$) then the $n \times n$ normal-equations matrix $\mathbf{N}_0 = \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{W}_0 \mathbf{A}$ is positive definite and the system (5) can be solved very efficiently with the Cholesky algorithm. This is the method currently used in GDAAS. Note that the Cholesky decomposition of \mathbf{N}_0 ends with an error flag (`ierr` > 0) if the matrix is not positive definite, e.g., because of too few observations.

In order to cope with outliers (item 2) the technique is to reduce the statistical weight of suspected outliers by a certain factor (≤ 1) depending on the size of the normalized right-hand side, $z_i = b_i/\sigma_i$, make a solution and recompute the right-hand sides (which are now the residuals of the least-squares solution) from which new weight reduction factors are computed, and iterate until convergence. The weight reduction factor originally proposed (in GAIA-LL-34) was of the ‘Hubert’ type:

$$h(z) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |z| < c \\ c(2|z| - c)z^{-2} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

with $c = 2$. (Note that both the original and second versions of GAIA-LL-034 contained typos in the definition of the Hubert metric $\rho(z) = z^2 h(z)$, but the accompanying Fortran implementation `whuber` was correct.) In an e-mail dated 2004 May 19, I proposed a different weight reduction function called `wdecay` in order to eliminate gross errors more quickly. The new function is

$$d(z) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |z| < 2 \\ 1 - 1.77373519609519t^2 + 1.14161463726663t^3 & \text{if } 2 \leq |z| < 3 \\ \exp(-|z|/3) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $t = |z| - 2$. The numerical constants are chosen to make a smooth transition from $d(z) = 1$ (for $|z| < 2$) to the exponential decay (for $|z| > 3$). The new function provides a much more dramatic weight reduction for large residuals; e.g. at 10 sigmas we have $d(10) \simeq 0.0357$ instead of $h(10) = 0.36$, while at 100 sigmas we have $d(100) \simeq 3.33 \times 10^{-15}$ versus $h(100) = 0.0396$.

Using downweighting we simply replace the original weight matrix \mathbf{W}_0 with the modified weight matrix $\mathbf{W} = \text{diag}[d(z_1)\sigma_1^{-2}, \dots, d(z_1)\sigma_m^{-2}]$ and solve the modified normal equations

$$\mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{b} \quad (8)$$

for the update \mathbf{x} . The normal equations matrix $\mathbf{N} = \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{A}$ must be recomputed and decomposed after each update, since \mathbf{W} depends on the residuals in the previous iteration.

The proper treatment of outliers in current GIS experiments is severely hampered by two practical problems. The first is that the iterations required for settling the weight reduction factors are very time consuming because they are not made internally in the Source Updating algorithm but by calling the algorithm several times sequentially. Thus, there is probably a lot of unnecessary data shuffling between the iterations.

The second problem is related to the fact that the outlier detection requires a rather precise estimate of the variances of the residuals that are not considered to be outliers, in order to be able to reject those that really are (and only those). There is currently no self-consistent estimation of these variances: they are just taken to be the nominal variances increased by an *ad hoc* assumed contribution from other errors (given by the specified σ_{Param}). A better way is to make a robust estimation of the variances at the same time as the parameters are updated. The mechanism for this is explained in the next section.

3 The new algorithm

3.1 Use of SVD

Introduce the normalized observation equations matrix

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{W}^{1/2} \mathbf{A} \quad (9)$$

and the normalized right-hand side vector

$$\hat{\mathbf{b}} = \mathbf{W}^{1/2} \mathbf{b} \quad (10)$$

That is, the i th row in \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{b} is multiplied by $d(z_i)^{1/2}/\sigma_i$, $i = 1 \dots m$. The weighted least-squares problem is now to minimize $|\hat{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{b}}|$.

In the proposed new algorithm, we do not use the normal equations (8) to find \mathbf{x} but solve the (over-determined) system $\hat{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x} \sim \hat{\mathbf{b}}$ directly by means of a Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$. That is, we find an $m \times n$ matrix \mathbf{U} , a diagonal $n \times n$ matrix \mathbf{S} and an $n \times n$ matrix \mathbf{V} such that

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{V}^T \quad (11)$$

The orthonormal columns of \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} are the left and right singular vectors of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$, respectively, and $\mathbf{S} = \text{diag}(s_1, \dots, s_n)$ contains the singular values in descending order, $s_1 \geq s_2 \geq \dots \geq s_n \geq 0$. Now define $\mathbf{S}^+ = \text{diag}(s_1^+, \dots, s_n^+)$ where

$$s_j^+ = \begin{cases} s_j^{-1} & \text{if } s_j \geq \epsilon s_1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Here $0 < \epsilon < 1$ is a preset threshold value for the acceptable ratio of the smallest to the largest singular value. (Subsequently $\epsilon = 10^{-3}$ is adopted.) The rank (r) equals the number of non-zero elements in \mathbf{S}^+ . The required solution is then computed as

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{S}^+\mathbf{U}^T\hat{\mathbf{b}} \quad (13)$$

For a problem of full rank ($r = n$) this solution is mathematically equivalent to that obtained via the normal equations (8). However, if $r < n$ then the normals may be singular or nearly singular which means that a wide range of solutions satisfy the equations and the one actually computed may give a large and spurious update. By contrast, the pseudo-solution (13) in this case produces the unique solution with the minimum norm $|\mathbf{x}|$, so one can at least be sure that the source parameters are not modified unnecessarily.

The rank defect $n - r$ is one of the output arguments of the source updating algorithm. Normally it should be zero. Although a positive value should not invalidate the updating, as explained above, the results should be treated with some caution. In particular, the returned standard errors of the astrometric parameters may be considerably underestimated.

3.2 Internal iterations (outliers and model non-linearity)

The weight matrix \mathbf{W} includes the weight reduction factors $d(z_i)$, which depend on the residuals themselves. The solution must therefore be iterated for the outliers to receive their proper (low) weight. Experience shows that some 5 to 10 iterations are usually needed for this process to converge. However, it is not necessary to recompute the observation equations $[\hat{\mathbf{A}} \hat{\mathbf{b}}]$ from scratch for every such iteration. On the first iteration, the equations $[\hat{\mathbf{A}}_0 \hat{\mathbf{b}}_0]$ are saved before applying the weight reduction factors (that is, $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_0 = \mathbf{W}_0^{1/2} \mathbf{A}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_0 = \mathbf{W}_0^{1/2} \mathbf{b}$). The weight reduction is then applied, the SVD solution made and the parameters updated by \mathbf{x} . At the same time the right-hand side (before weight reduction) is modified as $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_0 := \hat{\mathbf{b}}_0 - \hat{\mathbf{A}}_0 \mathbf{x}$. From this, new weight reduction factors are computed and applied, and a new SVD solution made. This process is repeated until the updates become negligibly small. At that point the outliers have been properly identified, but the solution may still need some refinement because of the slight non-linearity of the observation model itself (item 3). To this end it is necessary to recompute the observation equations from scratch and make a few more iterations.

We see that the iterations are of two kinds: either with a full computation of the observation equations directly from the observation model, or an approximate computation of the right-hand side based on the linearized model. In terms of computing time the first one is much more demanding and should therefore be used as little as possible. The second one is much quicker but good enough for the several iterations required by the outlier detection.

The proposed algorithm makes a sequence of iterations controlled by the following parameters (with values as specified in the algorithm):

```

MAX_ITER = 30
ITER_RECOMPUTE = 6
MIN_RECOMPUTE = 1
A_SCALE(1:6) = (/ 5D-11, 5D-11, 5D-11, 1D-13, 1D-13, 1D-10 /)
RMS_UPDATE_LIMIT = 0.01

```

The first parameter is the maximum number of iterations allowed. The second parameter specifies the minimum interval at which the full observation equations are recomputed. The value 6 means that, in the worst case, the full equations are computed in iterations 1, 7, 13, 19 and 25. `MIN_RECOMPUTE` is the minimum number of times that the full observation equations must be recomputed (not counting the initial set-up). The six values in `A_SCALE` are typical ‘target accuracies’ for the six astrometric parameters (note that units are rad and rad day⁻¹). The iteration will stop when the RMS update relative to `A_SCALE` (see below) is less than `RMS_UPDATE_LIMIT`, provided that the full observation equations have

been recomputed at least `MIN_RECOMPUTE` times after the initial iteration. The equations are recomputed after the RMS update has become less than `RMS_UPDATE_LIMIT` or after `ITER_RECOMPUTE` iterations (since the last computation), whichever comes first.

One cannot specify a target accuracy for the sixth astrometric parameter μ_r , since its effect on the observed position depends on the size of the proper motion. This is why the RMS update is computed without including the update in the sixth parameter if $n = 6$.

The values in `A_SCALE` serve one more purpose, namely for preconditioning the observation equations. The condition number of the observation equations matrix depends on the choice of units for the astrometric parameters. The standard units (rad, rad day⁻¹) make the partial derivatives in \mathbf{A} differ by several orders of magnitude, which increases the condition number. This is a problem because we use a fixed limit ϵ on the ratio of the singular values to determine the rank of the equations, and it is not reasonable that the rank should depend on the units used. We solve this problem by using `A_SCALE(j)` as the unit for the j th astrometric parameter when computing the updates. Since the updates x_j are thus obtained in units of `A_SCALE(j)` the expression for the RMS update is simply

$$x_{\text{rms}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\min(n, 5)} \sum_{j=1}^{\min(n, 5)} x_j^2} \quad (14)$$

On the other hand, the parameter updating in (4) becomes $a_j := a_j + \text{A_SCALE}(j) \times x_j$ (but see Sect. 3.4).

3.3 Re-using partial derivatives

The astrometric data processed in the source updating usually consist of 11 consecutive observations in AF1–11. The absolute time and geometry are practically the same for all 11 observations, which means that A_{ij} is practically constant for the observations (i) belonging to the same FOV transit. We can exploit this by computing A_{ij} only for the observation in AF1 and simply copy this value to subsequent observations in AF2–11. The right-hand sides b_i are however rigorously computed for every observation.

3.4 Parameter updating

The spherical coordinates represented by the two first astrometric parameters (barycentric right ascension and declination at the reference epoch) have singularities at the poles. This means that the simplistic position updating formulae, $a_1 := a_1 + \text{A_SCALE}(1) \times x_1 / \cos a_2$ and $a_2 := a_2 + \text{A_SCALE}(2) \times x_2$ become inexact near the poles and might produce spurious results or even a division by zero. The update in proper motion is also affected, since the orientation of the proper motion axes depends on the position. To avoid this potential problem the new algorithm performs the updating in vector space rather than in spherical coordinates. Thus, the original parameters ($a_1 = \alpha_0$, $a_2 = \delta_0$, $a_4 = \mu_{\alpha*}$, $a_5 = \mu_\delta$) are transformed to a position vector \mathbf{r} and its time derivative $\dot{\mathbf{r}}$; the updates are similarly transformed and added to \mathbf{r} , $\dot{\mathbf{r}}$; and the results transformed back to spherical

coordinates and proper motion components. Given also a convention for the meaning of μ_{α^*} and μ_{δ} in the case when $\delta_0 = \pm 90^\circ$ exactly (such a convention is already embedded in the fundamental algorithms), this completely eliminates potential singularities or loss of precision near the poles.

3.5 Updating less than the full number of astrometric parameters

One input argument for the new source updating is n , the number of astrometric parameters to be updated. Normally it should be set to 5, in exceptional cases $n = 6$ may be used to estimate the perspective acceleration. Values of 2, 3 or 4 are also permitted. The parameters updated in each case is shown by the following table:

n	α	δ	π	μ_{α^*}	μ_{δ}	μ_r
2	×	×				
3	×	×	×			
4	×	×		×	×	
5	×	×	×	×	×	
6	×	×	×	×	×	×

3.6 Estimation of error sources not included in σ

In the old GIS, extraneous error sources were taken into account by quadratically adding an *a priori* contribution σ_{Param} to the standard error of the observation. The choice of σ_{Param} is difficult and may affect critically the convergence properties of GIS. Thus it is highly desirable to make each of the individual GIS processes adaptive, so that it automatically adjusts the standard errors based on the actual residuals. This feature is incorporated in the new algorithm.

However, rather than making an *additive* correction to the formal variances, we have chosen to make a *multiplicative* correction for each source. In practice the two approaches are usually nearly equivalent since the different observations of a given source usually have similar standard errors. However, the multiplicative correction is much easier to implement. Moreover, it also allows to correct the standard errors should they happen to be overestimated.

The multiplicative correction factor u applied to the given observational standard errors is called the ‘unit weight error’, UWE, and should ideally equal 1. It is computed as

$$u = 1.03125 \times \frac{|\hat{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{b}}|}{\sqrt{(\sum_{i=1}^m d_i) - r}} \quad (15)$$

where m is the number of observations and d_i the weight reduction factors. Thanks to the steep decrease of $d(z)$ beyond 2–3 sigmas, $\sum_i d_i$ is practically equal to the number of

retained observations. The factor

$$\sqrt{\frac{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d(z) \exp(-z^2/2) dz}{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} z^2 d(z) \exp(-z^2/2) dz}} = 1.031247 \dots \quad (16)$$

corrects for the systematic reduction of the RMS residual through the function $d(z)$ in case of purely gaussian z .

During each internal iteration the UWE is computed and applied to the observational standard errors before the weight reduction factors are computed. On the very first iteration an alternative, extremely robust method is used to estimate the UWE, namely as half the intersextile range of b_i/σ_i . This avoids that the iterations start off with most of the observations strongly downweighted in the common case when the initial residuals b_i are large compared with the standard errors.

3.7 Standard errors and correlations

The variance–covariance matrix of the astrometric parameters is obtained as the inverse of the normal equations matrix \mathbf{N} in the case of full rank. With the SVD we have from (9) and (11) $\mathbf{N} = \hat{\mathbf{A}}^T \hat{\mathbf{A}} = (\mathbf{U}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{V}^T)^T (\mathbf{U}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{V}^T) = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{S}^2\mathbf{V}^T$ (since $\mathbf{U}^T\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{I}$) from which $\mathbf{N}^{-1} = (\mathbf{V}\mathbf{S}^+)(\mathbf{V}\mathbf{S}^+)^T$ (since $\mathbf{V}^{-1} = \mathbf{V}^T$). The standard errors of the astrometric parameters, expressed in units of `A_SCALE`, are consequently

$$\sigma(a_j) = \sqrt{\sum_{\ell=1}^r (\mathbf{V}\mathbf{S}^+)_{j\ell}^2} \quad (17)$$

Note that $\sigma(a_j)$ implicitly includes the correction factor u for the unit weight variance discussed above. The correlation coefficients are similarly obtained as

$$\rho_{jk} = \frac{1}{\sigma(a_j)\sigma(a_k)} \sum_{\ell=1}^r (\mathbf{V}\mathbf{S}^+)_{j\ell} (\mathbf{V}\mathbf{S}^+)_{k\ell} \quad (18)$$

The above expressions for the standard errors and correlations can be used also in the case when $r < n$, but the results must be interpreted with great caution.

4 Organization of program modules and data

4.1 Program modules

The complete Fortran90 source code to run the source updating with test data is contained in the following modules:

`GaiaParam` – Gaia-2 Parameters (database dump)
`Source` – main program (for testing only)
`Astro` – package for source updating

Svd – package for Singular Value Decomposition (from LINPACK)
Misc – miscellaneous routines (**wdecay**, sorting, etc)
Qn – quaternion algebra
Qnsl – quaternion interface to analytical scanning law
Nsl_fm_017 – analytical scanning law (GAIA-FM-017)
Ephem – standard ephemerides for Gaia and planets
GR_Constants – fundamental algorithms
GR_Error – fundamental algorithms
GR_Parameters – fundamental algorithms
GR_Transformations – fundamental algorithms
GR_Vectors – fundamental algorithms

All system parameters (number of CCDs etc.) are defined through the module **GaiaParam**, generated by a dump of the live version of the Gaia Parameter Database made on 2004 July 14.

The main program in **Source** is meant for testing only. Note however that it contains a call to the routine **f2a**, which computes an initial approximation of the astrometric parameters from the observational data in the first FOV transit. This routine may be of interest for the initial data treatment and object matching.

The module **Astro** contains the source updating algorithm **sourceUpdate** and a number of service routines specifically used for the updating. Some of the more general routines (e.g. for the SVD, downweighting and quaternion algebra) have been put in separate modules.

The module **Nsl_fm_017** differs from the standard NSL routine in GAIA-FM-017 only in one line, where a modification was proposed by LL in order to allow continuous quaternion representation of the NSL. The modified routine returns the spin phase modulo 4π instead of modulo 2π .

The routines in **Ephem** and **GR_*** are included for completeness, but should be identical to current versions of these modules.

4.2 Structure of observational input data

The present Fortran90 version of the source updating algorithm assumes that the observational data can be transferred as a single array of length **nFovTrn** (= number of FOV transits of the source) and of a special data type (**AstroElementary**) based on the actual structure of the observations. The public declaration of the **AstroElementary** data type is as follows:

```

TYPE AstroElementaryHead
  INTEGER :: sourceId      ! source ID
  INTEGER :: fov           ! 1 or 2 for Astro1, 2
  INTEGER :: strip        ! CCD strip number for zeta
  INTEGER :: row           ! CCD row number (1 to 10)
  REAL (DOUBLE) :: column ! observed AC coordinate [pixel]
  REAL (DOUBLE) :: columnSE ! s.e. of column [pixel]

```

```

    REAL (DOUBLE) :: columnTime    ! time asociated with column [days]
    REAL (DOUBLE) :: rateAC        ! transverse rate [columns/strip]
END TYPE AstroElementaryHead

TYPE AstroElementaryUnit
    INTEGER :: valid                ! 1 if CCD transit is valid
    REAL (DOUBLE) :: obsTime        ! CCD transit time [days]
    REAL (DOUBLE) :: obsTimeSE      ! s.e. of transit time [days]
END TYPE AstroElementaryUnit

TYPE AstroElementary
    TYPE (AstroElementaryHead) :: head
    TYPE (AstroElementaryUnit) :: unit(MAX_N_ETA)    ! MAX_N_ETA = 11
END TYPE AstroElementary

```

In the source updating algorithm `sourceUpdate` the observations are transferred by means of the two arguments `nFovTrn` and `ae`, declared as:

```

    INTEGER :: nFovTrn
    TYPE (AstroElementary) :: ae(*)

```

However, *no direct reference is made* in `sourceUpdate` to the contents of the array `ae`. Instead, `nFovTrn` and `ae` are forwarded as arguments to the subroutine `sourceObsEqs`, which returns the observation equations and other data needed by `sourceUpdate`. Thus, the `sourceUpdate` code is actually independent of the precise structure of the observational data.

In `sourceObsEqs` the observations are forwarded, one FOV transit at a time, to a third subroutine called `calcResAE`. This is where the observational data are actually interpreted and compared with theoretical values. `calcResAE` is a mock-up routine which must be re-written to access the relevant attitude, calibration and global data. In the mock-up version the attitude access is simply represented by a subroutine call to the nominal scanning law (same as used to generate the observations), and similarly for the calibration and global data.

4.3 Test data

The test data for `sourceUpdate` are contained in the following text files:

```

source.prn – table of true astrometric parameters for 165 sources
AE.prn – simulated AstroElementary data for the 165 sources
upd.prn – output file generated by the main program

```

The table below gives an overview of the test sources. Number 1–100 have astrometric parameters generated by a random number generator. Except for the first 20 sources, a certain fraction of outliers are added to the AL observational data. ‘Independent’ means that the perturbations simulating outliers were given to the specified fraction of all the

elementary observations of the source (so that, in general, not more than one or two elementary observations are perturbed on any given FOV transit); ‘correlated’ means that all the ≤ 11 elementary observations of a given FOV transit were given the same perturbation (the fraction then refers to the fraction of perturbed FOV transits).

The 21 sources with significant perspective acceleration (Nos. 101–121) were taken from Table 1.2.3 in Vol. 1 of the Hipparcos and Tycho Catalogues (ESA SP–1200), using the catalogue values as ‘true’ parameters. For the next 21 sources the same stars were placed at $\sqrt{10}$ greater distances, but reducing the parallaxes and proper motions by this factor. This means that the perspective effect (which is proportional to $\pi\mu$) is reduced a factor 10. For Nos. 143–163 the same stars were placed at 10 times the original distances, reducing the perspective effect by another order of magnitude.

The astrometric data for the two polarissimae are:

No. 164: $\alpha = 40^\circ$, $\delta = +90^\circ$, $\pi = 0.5''$, $\mu_{\alpha*} = +0.4'' \text{ yr}^{-1}$, $\mu_\delta = +0.3'' \text{ yr}^{-1}$, $V_R = +100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

No. 165: $\alpha = 10^\circ$, $\delta = -90^\circ$, $\pi = 1 \mu\text{as}$, $\mu_{\alpha*} = +1 \mu\text{as yr}^{-1}$, $\mu_\delta = +2 \mu\text{as yr}^{-1}$, $V_R = 0$. These were included to verify that the source updating works as close to the poles as one can reasonably come.

A more detailed analysis of the results of the test run will not be given here. In general the behaviour seems to be quite satisfactory, with updated astrometric parameters within a few standard errors of their true values. A notable exception is the polarissima, No. 164, where the solution gives a parallax that is 15–20 standard deviations away from the true value (e.g., the 5-parameter solution gives $\pi = 499923.82 \pm 3.86 \mu\text{as}$ (the true value being 500000 μas). The reason for this discrepancy needs further investigation.

Source No.	Fraction of outliers	Extra s.d. for outliers	Remark
1–20	0	–	–
21–40	10%	10^{-8} rad	independent outliers for each elementary obs.
41–60	10%	10^{-8} rad	correlated over a FOV transit
61–80	10%	10^{-6} rad	correlated over a FOV transit
81–100	10%	10^{-4} rad	correlated over a FOV transit
101–121	0	–	stars with significant perspective acceleration
122–142	0	–	as 101–121, but with $(\pi, \mu_{\alpha*}, \mu_\delta) \times 10^{-0.5}$
143–163	0	–	as 101–121, but with $(\pi, \mu_{\alpha*}, \mu_\delta) \times 10^{-1}$
164	0	–	polarissima, large π and μ
165	0	–	polarissima, small π and μ